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Research Article

**SERUM CALCIUM AND ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE
LEVELS IN PATIENTS TAKING ANTIPILEPTIC DRUGS**Tayyab Zia¹, Omaila Ikram², Nimra Ghazal³,¹House Officer, Mayo Hospital, LahoreEmail: tayyab.ravian13@gmail.com²House Officer, Mayo Hospital, LahoreEmail omaila41@gmail.com³House Officer, Mayo Hospital, LahoreEmail nimraghazal21@outlook.com**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Millions of people in the world-wide are affected by a chronic condition of epilepsy. In world more or less 50 million people have a medical condition of this syndrome. In order to treat epileptic patient antiepileptic drugs are acting as a chief support. It is observed from findings that constant use of antiepileptic drugs are coupled with reduced bone mineral density and deformities in bone metabolism. Patients receiving antiepileptic drugs are more prone to the diseases of bone. Numerous biochemical irregularities of bone metabolism that consist of hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia, elevated alkaline phosphatase level, low vitamin D levels have been associated with the use of antiepileptic drug. This research will assist to establish the undesirable influences of these drugs on bones and regarding calcium and vitamin D supplements to be provided during the treatment with antiepileptic drugs.

OBJECTIVE: To determine frequency of hypocalcemia and elevated alkaline phosphatase levels in patients taking antiepileptic drugs.

STUDY DESIGN: Descriptive cross sectional

SETTING: The study was conducted in Department of Paediatric Medicine, Faisalabad

DURATION OF STUDY: Six month from the date of approval of synopsis from board of study March 10, 2017 till Sep 10, 2017

METHODOLOGY: In this study a total sample size was 95 patients Patient full summary including name, age, sex, hospital number, details of drugs and date of inclusion in study was noted down blood sample of 3 ml was taken and sent to laboratory for measuring serum levels of calcium and alkaline phosphatase. Test was performed in selectra pro XL machine using photometric method. In the pre-designed Performa, all statistics was entered.

RESULTS: Our study shows that mean age was 7 years with $SD \pm 2.713$. Fifty five percent children were male while 45% children were female. Sixty two percent children had Hypocalcaemia and seventy five percent children had raised alkaline phosphatase.

CONCLUSION: Our study concludes that 62% of epileptic children had hypocalcemia and 80% had raised alkaline phosphatase levels.

KEYWORDS: hypocalcemia, alkaline phosphatase levels, antiepileptic drugs.

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INTRODUCTION:

Millions of people in the world-wide are affected by a chronic condition of epilepsy. In world more or less 50 million people have a medical condition of this syndrome. In order to treat epileptic patient antiepileptic drugs are acting as a chief support [1]. It is observed from findings that constant use of antiepileptic drugs are coupled with reduced bone mineral density and deformities in bone metabolism [2, 3]. Patients receiving antiepileptic drugs are more prone to the diseases of bone. Numerous biochemical irregularities of bone metabolism that consist of hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia, elevated alkaline phosphatase level, low vitamin D levels have been associated with the use of antiepileptic drug [4].

These results have been confirmed in children and adults equally and it is widely noticed with antiepileptic drugs that induce cytochrome P450 enzymes like carbamazepine, phenytoin, sodium valproate. Such type of enzyme giving drugs may well boost catabolism of vitamin D which results in hypophosphatemia and hypocalcemia. In addition, it is found that antiepileptic drugs may possibly slow down cellular reaction to parathyroid hormones. These mechanisms have been suggested and may play an active part in enlarging the structure or form of bone [5].

Valproate drugs for example put forth an indirect influence on bone by changing renal function. There is not only single mechanism that appeared to give explanation of the biochemical alterations in connection with antiepileptic drugs but numerous healing therapies are accessible. For more than six months to 2 years a long-term therapy is linked with raised alkaline phosphatase and reduced calcium and phosphate [6]. Such transformations can direct to rickets. Use of antiepileptic chronically for few years causes 3-6 times greater than before threat of fractures as compared to common people [7].

A study carried out in India showed that with chronic use of antiepileptic drugs 61% of children had hypocalcemia and 79% had raised alkaline phosphatase levels [8]. Similarly, in another study in India, 68% of epileptic children had hypocalcemia [9]. However, an investigation performed in Germany based on the chronic use of antiepileptic showed that over 75% of children were suffered from hypocalcemia and elevated alkaline phosphatase levels. [10] In department of neurosurgery, Alzahra University Hospital a study carried out showed that in adult patients taking antiepileptics valproate therapy does not appear to alter bone turnover [11]. Calcium level in patient taking valproic acid is 9.2 0.2 and in control 9.0

(0.2). Alkaline phosphatase level in case is 184 16.9 and in control 170 25.6. This research is important, however, because on serum calcium and alkaline phosphatase the effect of antiepileptics is on debate. This research will assist to establish the undesirable influences of these drugs on bones and regarding calcium and vitamin D supplements to be provided during the treatment with antiepileptic drugs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This research was conducted in Department of Paediatric medicine Faisalabad, six months after approval from the hospital ethical review committee. Patients having age between 3-12 years and both gender and patients receiving antiepileptic drugs (sodium valproic acid, carbamazepine, phenobarbitone) for at least 6 months duration.

Hypocalcemia was defined as serum calcium level below 8.5 mg/dl. Raised Serum Alkaline Phosphatase Level was defined as serum alkaline phosphatase levels >300 IU/L. Antiepileptic Drug: Antiepileptic drugs used for at least 6 months in study are: i. Sodium valproate (10-60mg/dl) ii. Carbamazepine (10-35mg/dl) iii. Phenobarbitone (5-7mg/dl).

Exclusion criteria: Children suffering from cerebral palsy, additional causes of secondary osteoporosis like malabsorption, chronic kidney disease and chronic liver disease, children on medications like immunosuppressant drugs and steroids, patients having baseline hypocalcemia and elevated alkaline phosphatase and patients who are bed ridden were excluded from the study.

Authorization of institutional research forum of KRL and ethical review committee was taken selection of all patients meeting inclusion criteria. After explaining significance of research permission was taken from parents/guardians Patient full summary including name, age, sex, hospital number, details of drugs and date of inclusion in study was noted down blood sample of 3 ml was taken and sent to laboratory for measuring serum levels of calcium and alkaline phosphatase. Test was performed in selectra pro XL machine using photometric method. In the pre-designed performa all statistics was entered.

The analysis was carried out on software SPSS version 19. For numerical variable such as age, duration of drug, levels of calcium and alkaline phosphatase mean and standard deviation was analyzed. In order to establish children with hypocalcemia and elevated levels of alkaline phosphatase frequencies together with percentages was calculated. Effect modifier like age, gender, duration of antiepileptic, type of antiepileptic drug

was controlled by stratification. Post stratification chi square test was applied in which P value ≤ 0.05 will be considered as significant value.

68(72%) children were in age range 3-7 years while 27(28%) children were in age range 8-12 years. Mean age was 7 years with SD ± 2.713 . (table No 1).

RESULTS:

In this study age distribution was analyzed as

Table-1: AGE DISTRIBUTION (n=95)

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
3 -7 years	68	72%
8-12 years	27	28%
Total	95	100%

Mean age was 7 years with SD ± 2.713 . Gender distribution was analyzed as 52(55%) children were male while 43(45%) children were female. (table No 2).

Table-2: GENDER DISTRIBUTION (n=95)

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Male	52	55%
Female	43	45%
Total	95	100%

Duration of drug was analyzed as 62(65%) children had drug from 6-9 months while 33(35%) children were had drug from 9-12 months. Mean duration of drug was 00 years with SD ± 2.713 . (table No 3).

Table-3: Duration of Drug (n=95)

DURATION OF DRUG	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
6 to 9 months	62	65%
9 to 12 month	33	35%
Total	95	100

Mean duration of drug was 8 months with SD ± 1.993

Type of drug was analyzed as 57(60%) children were using Sodium valp , 19(20%) children were using Carbamazepine, 19(20%) children were using Phenobarbitone. (table No 4).

Table-4: Type of Antiepileptic Drug (n=95)

TYPE OF ANTIEPILEPTIC DRUG	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Sodium valp	57	60%
Carbamazepine	19	20%
Phenobarbitone	19	20%
Total	95	100

Mean calcium level was 8 mg/dl with SD $\pm$ 1.818 while Mean serum alkaline phosphatase levels was 311 IU/L with SD $\pm$ 3.249. (table No 5,6).

Table-5: Calcium Level (n=95)

CALCIUM LEVEL	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
$\leq$ 8.5 mg/dl	59	62%
$>$ 8.5 mg/dl	36	38%
Total	95	100%

Mean calcium level was 8 mg/dl with SD $\pm$ 1.818

Table-6: Serum Alkaline Phosphates Levels (n=95)

SERUM ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE LEVELS	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
$\leq$ 300 IU/L	24	25%
$>$ 300 IU/L	71	75%
Total	95	100%

Mean serum alkaline phosphatase levels was 311 IU/L with SD $\pm$ 3.249

Hypocalcaemia was analyzed as 59(62%) children had hypocalcaemia while 36(38%) children didn't had hypocalcaemia. (table No 7).

Table-7: Hypocalcemia (n=95)

HYPOCALCEMIA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Yes	59	62%
No	36	38%
Total	95	100%

Raised alkaline phosphatase was analyzed as 71(75%) children had Raised alkaline phosphatase while 24(25%) children didn't had Raised alkaline phosphatase. (table No 8).

Table-8: Raised Alkaline Phosphatase (n=95)

RAISED ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Yes	71	75%
No	24	25%
Total	95	100%

Stratification of Hypocalcaemia and Raised alkaline phosphatase with respect to age, gender, duration of antiepileptic, type of antiepileptic drug is given in table no 9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16.

Table-9: Stratification Of Hypocalcemia W.R.T Age (n=95)

HYPOCALCEMIA	3-7 years	8-12 years	Total
Yes	42	17	59
No	26	10	36
Total	68	27	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.9135

Table-10: Stratification of Hypocalcemia W.R.T Gender (n=95)

HYPOCALCEMIA	Male	Female	Total
Yes	32	27	59
No	20	16	36
Total	52	43	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.9003

Table-11: Stratification of Hypocalcemia W.R.T Duration of Drug (n=95)

HYPOCALCEMIA	6 to 9 months	9 to 12 month	Total
Yes	38	21	59
No	24	12	36
Total	62	33	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.8224

Table-12: Stratification Of Hypocalcemia W.R.T Type of Antiepileptic Drug (n=95)

HYPOCALCEMIA	Sodium valp	Carbamazepine	Phenobarbitone	Total
Yes	35	12	12	59
No	22	7	7	36
Total	57	19	19	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.9852

Table-13: Stratification of Raised Alkaline Phosphatase W.R.T Age (n=95)

RAISED ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	3-7 years	8-12 years	Total
Yes	51	20	71
No	17	7	24
Total	68	27	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.9254

Table-14: Stratification Of Raised Alkaline Phosphatase W.R.T Gender (n=95)

RAISED ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	Male	Female	Total
Yes	39	32	71
No	13	11	24
Total	52	43	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.9482

Table-15: Stratification of Raised Alkaline Phosphatase W.R.T Duration of Drug (n=95)

RAISED ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	6 to 9 months	9 to 12 month	Total
Yes	46	25	71
No	16	8	24
Total	62	33	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.8673

Table-16: Stratification of Raised Alkaline Phosphatase W.R.T Type of Antiepileptic Drug (n=95)

RAISED ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	Sodium valp	Carbamazepine	Phenobarbitone	Total
Yes	43	14	14	71
No	14	5	5	24
Total	57	19	19	95

Chi square test was applied in which P value 0.9815

DISCUSSION:

Millions of people in the world-wide are affected by a chronic condition of epilepsy. In world more or less 50 million people have a medical condition of this syndrome. In order to treat epileptic patient antiepileptic drugs are acting as a chief support [1]. It is observed from findings that constant use of antiepileptic drugs are coupled with reduced bone mineral density and deformities in bone metabolism. [2, 3]

Patients receiving antiepileptic drugs are more prone to the diseases of bone. Numerous biochemical irregularities of bone metabolism that consist of hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia, elevated alkaline phosphatase level, low vitamin D levels have been associated with the use of antiepileptic drug.[4] These results have been confirmed in children and adults equally and it is widely noticed with antiepileptic drugs that induce

cytochrome P450 enzymes like carbamazepine, phenytoin, sodium valproate.

Our study shows that 72% children were in age range 3-7 years while 28% children were in age range 8-12 years. Mean age was 7 years with SD $\pm$ 2.713. Fifty five percent children were male while 45% children were female. Sixty five percent children had drug from 6-9 months while 35% children were had drug from 9-12 months. Mean duration of drug was 00 years with SD $\pm$ 2.713. Type of drug was analyzed as 60% children were using Sodium valp, 20% children were using carbamazepine, 20% children were using phenobarbitone. Sixty two percent children had hypocalcaemia and seventy five percent children had raised alkaline phosphatase

Similar results were observed in another study conducted by Salimpour H et al [12] in which

chronic use of antiepileptic drugs 61% of children had hypocalcemia and 79% had raised alkaline phosphatase levels.

Similar results were observed in another study conducted by Valvi C et al [13] in which 68% of epileptic children had hypocalcemia and 85% had raised alkaline phosphatase levels. Our results also correlated with another study conducted by Verrotti A et al [14] in which 75% of children were suffered from hypocalcemia and 86% children had elevated alkaline phosphatase levels.

Ghazvini MRA[15] had reported that in department of neurosurgery, Alzahra University Hospital, adult patients taking antiepileptics valproate therapy does not appear to alter bone turnover. Calcium level in patient taking valproic acid is 9.2 (0.2) and in control 9.0 (0.2). Alkaline phosphatase level in case is 184 (16.9) and in control 170 (25.6).

CONCLUSION:

Our study concludes that 62% of epileptic children had hypocalcemia and 80% had raised alkaline phosphatase levels.

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